

Grain quality and nutritional value

Effect of pyrite and NPK on nutritional quality of rice

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Nutritional quality of rice can vary with soil type, fertilizer, and soil amendment. We studied the effect of pyrite and NPK fertilizers on the biochemical and nutritive makeup of rice grain.

The soil was slightly saline-alkali with moderate pH and exchangeable sodium. Experimental treatments were 150, 300, and 600 kg pyrite/ha and 40-20-20, 80-40-40, and 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha in nine combinations. To ensure complete oxidation, pyrite was applied 10 d before transplanting Saket 4. Half the N as urea and all the P as single superphosphate and K as

muriate of potash were applied at transplanting; the remaining N was applied 30 d after transplanting.

Grain samples were harvested with a sickle, dried in an oven at 60 °C, hand-pounded to brown rice, ground to powder, and passed through a 60-mesh sieve. Defatted samples were used to determine proximate composition following standard procedures.

Protein and total free amino acids increased in most treatments (see

table). The highest value was with 600 kg pyrite and 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha. However, lysine and tryptophan content decreased slightly with pyrite and NPK application. Total carbohydrate (mainly starch) content declined slightly. Amylose content decreased progressively with increase in NPK.

It appears that protein synthesis and its accumulation in the grain intensified with pyrite and NPK, at the expense of carbohydrates. □

Influence of pyrite and NPK on nutritional quality of brown rice. Faizabad, India, 1985-86 wet season.

Character	Content (% dry basis)			LSD at 5%
	Control	Treatment		
		Range	Mean	
Protein	8.06	8.10-9.05	8.63	0.40
Total free amino acids	0.25	0.35-0.95	0.73	0.12
Lysine	0.30	0.22-0.30	0.26	0.04
Tryptophan	0.11	0.08-0.10	0.09	0.01
Total carbohydrates	78.67	71.44-77.48	74.34	2.46
Amylose	21.98	20.06-21.43	20.56	0.58

Milling characteristics of aromatic rices

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Long slender rice grains (an important quality character of aromatic rices) are more prone to breakage during milling than shorter grain rices. We evaluated brokens in 102 traditional aromatic varieties (120-140 d) received from the International Rice Germplasm Center Jun-Nov 1986 at MI.

Harvested rice was hand threshed, air-dried at 30 °C to 14% moisture, cleaned, and stored 4 mo at room temperature. Samples of 100 g rough rice were dehulled in the Satake Rice Machine, Type THU, and milled in the ONEPASS Rice Whitening and Caking Machine, Type MC250. Broken grains were separated by hand.

Table 1. Milling characteristics of aromatic rices evaluated Jun-Nov 1986 at IARI, India.

Shape and L:W	Hulling (%)		Milling (%)		Head rice recovery (%)		Varieties (no.)
	Range	Mean	Range	Mean	Range	Mean	
Group I. Slender, >3.00	74.0-80.6	77.9	65.4-72.8	68.7	32.0-68.4	47.5	71
Group II. Medium, 2.4-3.0	76.0-80.2	77.5	67.4-74.8	69.8	41.0-67.4	53.0	13
Group III. Bold, 2.0-2.39	76.6-79.6	77.8	65.4-73.4	70.4	38.8-66.8	54.5	10
Group IV. Round, <2	77.0-80.6	78.6	68.0-74.4	70.2	51.4-70.8	63.5	8

^aAs % brown rice.

Table 2. Varieties showing better hulling, milling, and head rice recovery. IARI, India, 1986.

IRGC acc. no.	Name	Hulling (70)	Milling (%)	Head rice recovery (%)	Country
Group I					
27796	Basmati Surbh 161	78.2	71.4	68.4	Pakistan
27821	Basmati 370A	78.6	70.4	65.4	Pakistan
Group II					
27802	Basmati 106-12	76.2	69.8	67.4	Pakistan
Group III					
27815	Basmati 213	79.6	13.4	66.8	Pakistan
60008	Xiang Geng Dao	76.8	70.2	66.6	China
Group IV					
5896	Ambemohar 159	75.2	71.4	70.8	India

Varieties were classified into four groups on the basis of grain length-to-width ratio. The ranges of variation in hulling and milling percentage in all four groups were similar, suggesting that these characters are independent of grain shape (Table 1). However,

head rice recovery increased with a decrease in L:W, to a 63.5% average in the round-grain group.

Varieties with high head rice recovery and better hulling and milling qualities are listed in Table 2. Accessions 27796 and 27821 may be

better choices for improving these characteristics in long- and slender-grain, high-yielding varieties. In addition, accessions 27790, 27792, 27829, and 27830 in group I; 27802 and 27816 in group II; and 733 in group IV gave 80% hulling. □

Disease resistance

Reaction of rice germplasm to sheath blight (ShB)

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We evaluated 1,200 varieties and lines

for resistance to ShB during wet seasons (May-Dec) of 1986, 1987, and 1988. Each entry was transplanted in 3 rows (2 m long) 21 d after seeding at 20- × 15-cm spacing. ShB infection was rated during panicle emergence and at initiation of ripening.

Each entry was also tested in the laboratory through artificial

inoculation (detached leaf method) with isolates of *Thanatephorus cucumeris*. Of the lines evaluated, 19 showed good tolerance for ShB (see table). Considering days to 50% flowering, plant height, panicle numbers, panicle length, and yield, HM34-6-4-F and F47 appear promising. □

Promising rice cultivars with tolerance for ShB and their agronomic traits in Andaman, India. 1986-88 wet seasons.^a

Cultivar	Cross	Disease score ^b		Days to 50% flowering	Height (cm)	Panicles /plant (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Yield/plant (g)
		Field	Laboratory					
HM23-3	IR29/Rasi	4	2	90	122.8	6.2	23.6	20.1
HM33A-2-1-1-2F	Mirikrak/Ngoba	3	4	94	114.3	5.9	24.3	20.8
HM22-25-7-121	IR29/Ngoba	5	2	96	116.3	6.4	24.4	20.7
DR92	Released variety	5	3	98	123.8	8.5	26.0	22.2
F47	CCI47F-112-18-4-106	1	1	92	113.7	6.5	22.4	19.4
HM33A-21-2	Mirikrak/Ngoba	2	1	92	113.2	6.5	22.5	19.2
HM37-16-7-110-1	DR92/Pusa 33	3	3	68	116.2	6.8	18.2	18.8
HM22-18-1-132	IR29/Ngoba	3	2	113	125.3	8.9	23.5	16.8
HM46-1-21-F	IR28/Pawnbuh/IR28	3	1	98	121.2	8.2	23.8	13.9
HM23-2	IR29/Rasi	4	1	94	116.7	4.4	20.8	13.4
HM22-2-5-402	IR29/Ngoba	4	1	108	108.5	8.6	23.1	23.1
HM131-1-33	Mirikrak/Rasi	2	1	105	109.4	8.7	21.6	13.1
HM34-6-1-1	Mirikrak/Rasi	4	1	90	109.1	8.7	22.8	17.4
HM34-6-4-F	Mirikrak/Rasi	1	1	88	112.7	8.9	24.9	28.5
HM44-30-7-1	IR28/Ngoba/IR28	2	2	90	108.7	7.4	24.0	16.3
HM16-2-6-1	IR29/Ngoba	3	1	88	119.1	8.3	19.6	12.3
HM33A-5-7-F	Mirikrak/Ngoba	2	3	86	103.3	7.1	21.8	12.8
HM19-7	IR29/Khonorullo	4	3	98	116.6	6.2	26.1	19.0
HM22-23-4	IR29/Ngoba	2	5	95	110.6	6.0	22.0	15.7
Mashuri (local check)	Released variety	7	3	112	144.0	6.8	22.5	19.9

^a Data are means of 1986, 1987, and 1988. ^b Standard evaluation system for rice.

Genetic sources for resistance to rice blast (BI) caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. in Guilan Province, Iran

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We tested 1,265 rice cultivars in B1 screening nurseries at Rasht, Roudsar, and Bandar-Anzali 1978-84. In addition to natural infection, some artificial inoculations were made using conidial suspensions of international races identified in Guilan and from lesions on heavily infected leaves

collected at the 3- to 4-leaf stage from different areas. Each year, susceptible entries were dropped and resistant entries tested against some additional strains the following year.

All cultivars except seven Iranian cultivars were susceptible to the races and strains tested (see table). There